

THE IMPORTANCE OF FINANCIAL STATEMENT ANALYSIS IN ASSESSING THE EFFICIENCY OF THE COMPANY

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ANNOTATION

Nowadays, by the requirements of the decision PQ-4611 dated February 24, 2020, of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On additional measures for the transition to international standards of financial reporting", many companies started preparing their reports in accordance with international standards. Hence, making financial reports by a single standard helps users to compare the information of companies, and to identify potential problems and economic risks. Analysis of financial statements plays an important role in analyzing the company's economic condition, liquidity, profitability, risk, solvency, efficiency of operations, and proper use of funds. It also shows the trend or comparison of financial performance which is useful in making investment decisions by the shareholders of the company. This article examines the importance of the analysis of financial statements in decision-making, including the analysis of the accounting system, planning and control, and the parties using financial statements, the coefficients of financial standards.

Keywords: accounting, international standards, financial reporting, financial standards ratios, liquidity, solvency, activity, profitability ratios

Introduction. The economic reforms and liberalization of the economy in our country, and the creation of accounting based on national and international standards require an improvement of financial analysis methods for decision-making for effective use of resources. In the modernization of the economy of any country, accounting is closely related to the analysis and control of financial results.

The results of financial reports play a leading role in managing the organization, attracting investments, and making the right investment policy. In the process of transition in the market economy, the demands placed on accounting are increasing. It is also important that it meets the requirements of international standards, that internal and external information meets the needs of users, and that financial analyzes are accurate and transparent in making decisions and improving business efficiency.[1-4]

Ensuring the reliability and transparency of financial statements, and the presentation of data in precise dimensions, the comparison of results is achieved by accounting and financial analysis. Analysis of the achieved results and evaluation of the company's efficiency will help to justify its future development prospects. [5] In this regard, the question of increasing the informativeness and reliability of the information obtained based on the interpretation of accounting and reporting data becomes very relevant and practically important. Due to rapidly changing economic realities, the analysis of financial results is taking shape as a new methodological approach as one of the most sensitive indicators of the financial performance of enterprises to these changes.

Analysis of literature on the topic. In the current period, several professional studies have been conducted in order to interpret accounting and reporting data, to increase the importance of useful data, and evaluate and determine directions for its improvement. Creation and analysis of financial reports using world experience remain an urgent issue of our time. In this regard,

the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the strategy of actions for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" defines the following priorities: further development of international economic cooperation, including relations with leading international and foreign financial institutions expansion, a continuation of a well-thought-out foreign debt policy, effective use of it. [4]

In addition, in this regard, various economists and practitioners gave the following definitions based on their scientific point of view. For example, according to Professor L.T. Gilyarovskaya, "Financial statement analysis is the process of reviewing and analyzing a company's financial statements in order to obtain future earnings and make better economic decisions." According to D.V. Ostin, another scientist, "Understanding financial ratios is the activity of comparing one number in a financial statement by dividing it by another number. Comparisons of reporting results are made between the components of the financial statements or between the components that exist between them. Comparable figures may be figures from a different period or within the same period.". In addition, Atabaeva, Z.A. commented on the transparency of financial analysis in attracting investments, while Qudbiyev, N. T. commented on the importance of the analysis results in the effective system control and internal audit in their scientific works. In this sentence, one of the world's scientists, Professor Adam Hayes, spoke about information gaps in database and financial analysis. [3-6-8]

Today, there is never enough accounting literature and scientific articles on the importance of data analysis. Therefore, the issue of financial statement analysis and interpretation is an urgent topic on the agenda.

Research methodology. In writing the article, a systematic and comparative analysis, a study of the possibilities of analyzing and interpreting

financial results for national and foreign users of accounting reports, and information processing methods were carried out.

Analysis and results. The term financial statement analysis is also known as financial statement analysis and interpretation. It identifies the financial strengths and weaknesses of a business by establishing a meaningful relationship between the two financial statements, particularly the income statement and the closing balance sheet. Analysis of financial statements helps to measure the profitability, liquidity, efficiency, and solvency of the enterprise. The main purpose of financial statement analysis is to understand and diagnose financial statement data, and to determine the profitability and financial strengths of the business.

1. Financial statement analysis: concept and meaning

The information in the accounting report is created for various reasons and according to the needs of the users. However, the information disclosed in the financial statements may not be sufficient from the point of view of all interested parties. Users of accounting information are interested in drawing conclusions for decision-making purposes based on information included in financial statements. Information for such conclusions may not be available in the financial statements. For example, we cannot directly know the real profitability, liquidity, efficiency, and solvency of the business from the financial statements. For this purpose, the information in the financial report is analyzed on the basis of financial report indicators and other relevant additional information.

1.1 Meaning of analysis

Analysis means establishing a meaningful relationship between different items of two financial statements so that conclusions can be drawn.

1.2 Meaning of financial statement analysis

Analysis of financial statements is a general name for tools and methods designed to provide relevant information for making important policy decisions.

The term financial statement analysis is also known as financial statement analysis and interpretation. It establishes a meaningful relationship between the various items of the two financial statements, namely the income statement and the statement of financial position. It identifies the financial strengths and weaknesses of the business. [3] Analysis of financial statements helps to measure the profitability, liquidity, efficiency and solvency of the enterprise. Analysis of financial statements mainly consists of studying the relationship between various financial factors in a business, which is disclosed in one set of reports, and studying the trends of these factors as shown in a series of reports. [8]

Table 1

Financial statement analysis roadmap

Source: Prepared by the author

2. Parties using financial statements

In the business process, it is important to have and use the necessary information to effectively manage structures and make rational decisions. Processing financial data into useful information can improve productivity and benefit many decision makers. [7] Everyone concerned with the state of the business is interested in the financial statements of the enterprise. The following parties are extensive users of financial statement analysis.

- **Management:** Management wants to know the profitability, liquidity, efficiency and stability of the business so that the strengths and weaknesses of the business can be identified and effective business plans can be developed.
- **Shareholders:** Shareholders are interested in knowing the earning capacity of the business and its future growth. Shareholders are not directly involved in the day-to-day operations of the company, but they want to know the true profitability with the help of financial statements.
- **Creditors:** Creditors need to know whether the financial position of the business is good or bad. They are also interested in knowing whether the company will be able to pay the interest and also whether it will be able to repay the bonds before maturity.
- **Lending agencies:** Lending agencies and banks want to know the solvency of the business. They also want to know whether the money given as loan is safe or not.
- **Creditors:** Business creditors are interested in the short-term and long-term financial stability of the business. They want to know the ability of the business to meet debts and claims.

- **Employees:** The employees of a company have a vested interest in the profits of the business. If there are sufficient profits, unions have a moral basis to demand higher wages. Company employees are paid bonuses based on productivity and profitability, so they are interested in the financial analysis of the business.
- **Government:** Various government agencies study profitability and turnover ratios for purposes of taxation, regulation and nationalization. Financial statements also help the government to prepare national accounts.
- **Tax authorities:** Tax authorities are interested in knowing the profitability of the business in order to collect income tax. Likewise, sales tax authorities are interested in selling a business.
- **Economists and researchers:** These parties are interested in the financial performance of the business, they study the financial position of the enterprise, study the financial growth rate and compare it with other business enterprises and finally can suggest measures to increase the growth rate effectively.
- **Society:** the company originates and develops in society and it is part of society. He must fulfill his obligations to society. By analyzing the financial statements, society or the public gets information about how the company has fulfilled its social responsibilities and the methods.

Every employee involved in the analysis of the financial and economic activity of the enterprise, as well as using financial reporting data, must be able to read and analyze the balance sheet and other forms, in order to understand their articles, economic categories and indicators that describe them, as well as make effective conclusions and recommendations. [3]

3. Indicators of financial measurement standards

The main purpose of financial statement analysis is to understand and diagnose financial statement data, to determine the profitability and financial

strengths of the business. The purpose of such an analysis depends on the party interested in the analysis and its object, and when creating a conclusion about the state of the enterprise, the results can be compared to the following table:

2 - table

Standard ratios of financial statement analysis

Indicators	Very good	Good	Satisfactory	Not good
Liquidity ratio				
Current ratio	1.75-2	1.5-1.74	1.24-1.49	<1.25
Quick ratio	1	0.75-0.99	0.5-0.74	0.5
Cash to liability ratio	>0.1	0.07-0.09	0.06-0.04	<0.04
Solvency ratio				
Debt to assets ratio	0-0.09	0.09-0.16	0.17-0.24	0.25
Debt to equity ratio	0-0.39	0.40-0.69	0.7-0.24	0.25
Long term debt to assets ratio	0-0.09	0.1-0.29	0.3-0.49	>0.5
Long-term debt-to-equity ratio	0-0.09	0.9-0.16	0.17-0.24	0.25
Profitability				
Profit margin	>0.3	0.21-0.29	0.14-0.2	0.07-0.13
Return on assets	0.15	0.07-0.14	0.01-0.06	<0.01
Return on capital	>0.21	0.1-0.2	0.01-0.09	<0.01
Activity coefficient				

Fixed asset turnover	>1.1x	0.6x-0.9x	0.5x-0.2x	< 0.2x
Average collection period	60 days	30-59 days	9-29 days	< 9 days
Total asset turnover	> 1.1x	0.6x-0.9x	0.5x-0.2x	< 0.2

Source : Author by prepared

From the measurement of the financial results in the table above, it is possible to draw the following conclusion: the existence of the financial report, the activity of the company in a certain period can be known. If the company's performance is good, it can be said that the company is running its business effectively. A company's long-term performance, efficiency and survival in a growing market depends on the number of continuous individual and collective decisions made by management.

As an example, the financial results of joint-stock companies that have been operating in the Republic of Uzbekistan for many years were given and their analysis was considered one by one:

"**Uzbekkomir**" JSC is based on the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 290 dated June 21, 2004, from the "Komir" joint-stock association, which was established in 1994 on the basis of the "Sredazugol" production association determined reorganization by the Ministry of Coal Industry of the USSR. The main activity of the enterprise is mining of coal and white coal in the territories of the Republic of Uzbekistan and processing of mines in open and underground methods. [11]

3 – table

Financial results of "UZBEKKOMIR COAL MINING AND SALES" Joint Stock Company

"UZBEKKUR COAL MINING AND SALES" JSC					
	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Current Assets	479 054 082	619 727 383	490 985 639	534 108 804	536 757 539
Funds	11 717 798	9 508 652	27 449 360	5 743 202	2 615 182
Current liabilities	150 886 296	236 650 391	195 964 289	296 350 559	335 040 784
Current ratio	3.17	2.62	2.51	1.80	1.60
Cash ratio	0.078	0.040	0.140	0.019	0.008
Total assets	1 721 701 438	2 498 396 842	2 40 1889 454.00	2 549 880 719	2 395 183 776
Total liabilities	545 319 056	1 636 089 420	1 652 057 652.00	1 753 314 938	1 583 252 900
Debt to Assets Ratio	0.32	0.65	0.69	0.69	0.66
Income	324 369 277	453 569 290	485 107 873	664 043 778	971 472 664
Profit / Loss	59 462 672	5 434 188	-79 745 080	-183 811 666	20 559 564
Profit Margin	18%	1%	-16%	-28%	2%
Fixed asset turnover	0.15	0.19	0.20	0.27	0.41

Source: Corporate Information portal of the Ministry of Economy and Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan

"SHARGUNKOMIR" coal mine started in 1943. A 12-kilometer-long railway branch was built from the "Sariosia" railway station to "Takhkiyan" (now the city of Shargun), an 18- kilometer cable car for transporting coal, employees and goods. a 20-kilometer highway was built for transportation. In 1958, the Shargunkomir coal mine was put into operation, with a projected capacity of

400,000 tons per year. To date, according to the decisions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-2264 dated November 17, 2014 and No. 161 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 6, 2013, 101.3 million dollars (own funds are 11.8 million dollar, Chinese Eximbank loan - 89.5 million dollars) it is planned to implement the project of modernization of "Shargunkomir" joint stock company. [12]

4 - table

"SHARGUNKIMIR" Financial results of the Joint Stock Company

"SHARGUNKIMIR" JSC					
	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Current Assets	40 863 918	27 133 483	45 038 928	32 679 481	29 113 969
Funds	520 672	1 622 463	2 664 636	1 574 161	507 490
Current liabilities	22 696 689	29 480 788	65 144 606	97 507 805	136 241 788
Current ratio	1.80	0.92	0.69	0.34	0.21
Cash ratio	0.023	0.055	0.041	0.016	0.004
Total assets	52 495 947	261 190 871	534 351 944	765 591 779	1 020 357 293
Total liabilities	42 759 058	237 656 964	516 912 748	745 583 781	994 607 942
Debt to Assets Ratio	0.81	0.91	0.97	0.97	0.97
Income	20 374 481	47 066 563	622 55 767	70 063 267	102 298 778
Profit / Loss	7 006 652	11 656 348	-265 1947	5 296 013	53 000

Profit Margin	34%	25%	-4%	8%	0%
Fixed asset turnover	0.13	0.12	0.10	0.08	0.10

Source: Corporate Information Portal of the Ministry of Economy and Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan

- **Liquidity ratio:** According to Adam Hayes (2023), liquidity ratio is to determine the relationship between current assets and current liabilities. Defines the liquidity ratio as a ratio that measures the company's ability to meet its short-term financial obligations. Liquidity ratio: Current ratio; It consists of short term ratio and Cash ratio. [8]

It is possible to see the level of the company's ability to quickly cover its short-term obligations from the current ratio. Table 5 shows the ratio of current assets to current liabilities of "Uzbekkomir" JSC and "Shargunkomir" JSC with 5-year dynamics. According to the table, 2018 was a good indicator for both companies: "Uzbekkomir" JSC achieved a ratio of 3.17 and "Shargunkomir" JSC 1.8 . In the mining industry, anything above 1.75 means a very good result (Table 2). However, short-term solvency ratios of both companies decreased, and by 2021, JSC "Uzbekkomir" returned a result of 1.8 , while "Shargunkomir" JSC gave a very bad indicator with a coefficient of 0.34 .

5 – table

(Ratio of Current Assets to Current Liabilities) in Coal Mining Enterprises

Source: Prepared by the author

The ratio of the company's ability to cover short-term obligations with funds is shown in table 6. According to him, both enterprises started 2018 with a very low index, and only in 2020 "Uzbekkomir" JSC showed a very good result with a ratio of 0.14 . But the indicators of the last two years mean that next funds for covering short-term profits in enterprises are not satisfactory. "Uzbekkomir" JSC has a ratio of 0.008 , while "Shang'unkomir" JSC ended the year with a ratio of 0.004 . This instead suggests that any figure below 0.04 is *unsatisfactory for the industry*.

6 - table

Cash Ratios at Coal Mining Enterprises (*Ratio of Cash to Current Liabilities*)

Source: Prepared by the author

- Solvency ratio: According to Will Kenton (2022), this ratio measures the ability of a company to meet its long-term obligations. A solid company is one whose total debt does not exceed total assets. Solvency ratio: Debt-to-asset ratio; Debt to equity ratio; Ratio of long-term debt to Capital; It includes the ratio of long-term debt to assets.

The following table shows the ratio of total liabilities of enterprises to their assets in the dynamics of the year. According to table 7, in 2018, JSC "Uzbekkomir" showed a ratio of 0.32 , while JSC "Shang'unkomir" returned an unsatisfactory result with an indicator of 0.81 . According to the table 2, any indicator higher than 0.25 means that the debt situation of the enterprise is not satisfactory. It can be seen that the indebtedness of both companies will only increase in the coming years. This means that the ratio of the company's liabilities to all its main assets has increased.

7 – table

Ratio of Liabilities to Fixed Assets in Coal Mining Enterprises

Source: Prepared by the author

- **Activity Ratio:** According to Will Kenton (2020), the activity ratio is a ratio that measures a company's ability to utilize its assets. Jumingan (2019) operating ratio defines as a ratio to evaluate a company's day-to-day operations or ability to sell, collect receivables and utilize assets. The activity coefficient includes: Average collection period; Turnover of fixed assets; and takes Total Asset Turnover.

One of the most important indicators that evaluates the efficiency of the enterprise is the Activity ratio. Table 8 shows the extent to which coal mining enterprises are actively using their capital equipment. According to the table, in 2018, "Uzbekkomir" JSC reported a ratio of *0.15*, while "Shang'unkomir" JSC had a ratio of *0.13*. The industry standard coefficient indicates that any performance less than 0.2 times is unsatisfactory. But in both enterprises, the indicators continued to grow for years, and by 2022, Uzbekkomir JSC showed a very good result with a ratio of *0.41*, and Shargunkomir JSC remained with a ratio of *0.10*. The analysis of these results means that "Uzbekkomir" JSC has achieved a very good level in the use of its main assets and has given positive growth indicators in the dynamics of the last 5 years. Although the activity of JSC "Shargunkomir" is positive in other coefficients, it means that the indicator of effective use of its main resources is low.

8 - table

Turnover of Fixed Assets in Coal Mining Enterprises

Source: Prepared by the author

- Profitability ratio: According to Adam Hayes, this ratio measures a company's ability to make a profit at a given level of sales, assets and share capital. The profitability ratio consists of: Profit margin; Return on assets; and Return on Equity. [8]

Profitability ratio is one of the indicators that shows the efficiency of the enterprise and attracts investors the most. According to the table 9, "Uzbekkomir" JSC showed a very good indicator in 2018-2019, 34% and 25%. In 2018, "Shargunkomir" JSC showed a standard satisfactory indicator of 18%, *but in the coming years, the company's profit margin dropped sharply and even loss*

indicators were observed. In fact, in 2020 both companies suffered from economic crisis. By the last few years, we can see that coal mining companies have recovered their profits and risen above the break-even point.

9 – table

Annual dynamics of Profit Margin in coal mining enterprises

Source: Prepared by the author

The analysis of financial reports gives an opportunity to understand how the enterprise received income, record expenses during the reporting period, and forms financial results. Based on this information, provides an opportunity to analyze the most important indicators of the company's performance, regardless of the industry. This, in turn, enables the users of accounting information to make correct and effective decisions.

Conclusions and suggestions. With the help of analysis of financial results, it is possible to clearly see the financial stability of the campaign, the ability to cover the short-term and long-term debt, maintain liquidity and stable profitability, the ability to use its assets and liabilities with single-digit measurements and draw up financial plans based on these results.

In our rapidly developing country, the analysis of financial results is very important in monitoring the financial situation of enterprises, controlling them, and making the right decisions. We can learn from the coal mining joint-stock companies given as an example that one indicator alone is not enough to determine the general performance of the enterprise. If *the Liquidity ratio was used* to determine the company's ability to cover its short-term debts, *the Solvency ratio* was used to determine the ratio of its long-term liabilities. These indicators play an important role in determining the economic situation of the enterprise, making management decisions, and attracting banks and creditors.

In order to monitor the efficiency in the management of enterprises, *the efficiency coefficients* were used to determine the extent to which the purchased fixed assets are being efficiently used. These coefficients include such important indicators as the turnover of material reserves, the ratio of cash to semi-finished products, and the turnover of fixed assets. In its place, it helps to reveal the annual dynamics of the company's growth from a different perspective, creating a necessary database for decisions made by the management.

The Profitability coefficient of the enterprise is very important in ensuring transparency in the financial statements of the enterprise and attracting foreign investors. With the help of these indicators, it is possible to determine the gross profit, cost-to-income ratio, and profit margins of the enterprise based on the same dimensions and to compare them with the indicators of the previous period. Profitability indicators in joint-stock companies show the stability of the enterprise and help it take its place in the stock market.

In conclusion, drawing up the analysis of financial statements on the basis of one standard helps to compare mutual information, to identify possible problems and economic risks. In the right use, it helps to make the necessary decisions by clarifying whether the company's assets and liabilities correspond to its financial and economic activities, and whether the resources are properly distributed or not.

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